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Scientific programme of Social Work International Conferences

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Direction:

Ivana Acocella (University of Florence, Italy)
Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence, Italy)

Authors:

Ivana Acocella (University of Florence, Italy)
Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence, Italy)
Teres Hjärpe (University of Lund, Sweden)
Silvia Pezzoli (University of Florence, Italy)
Francesca Rizzuto (University of Palermo, Italy)
Annalisa Tonarelli (University of Florence, Italy)
Laura María Zanón Bayón-Torres (Pontifical University Comillas, Spain)

Reviewers:

Roberta Teresa Di Rosa (Università degli Studi di Palermo, Italy)
Paula Rodríguez Aznar (Universidad de Granada, Spain)
Ana María Huesca González (Pontifical University Comillas, Spain)
Norma Montesino (University of Lund, Sweden)
M^a Belén Morata García de la Puerta (University of Granada, Spain)

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Partners of the Global-ANSWER Project: University of Granada (Granada, Spain), Comillas Pontifical University of Madrid (Madrid, Spain), Red Acoge (Madrid, Spain), Bayt Al-Thaqafa (Barcelona, Spain), Diversidades (Vigo, Spain), Rioja Acolle (La Rioja, Spain), City Council of Granada (Granada, Spain), University of Palermo (Palermo, Italy), City Council of Palermo (Palermo, Italy), University of Florence (Florence, Italy), Oxfam Italia (Florence, Italy), FNAS-Fondazione Nazionale Assistenti Sociali (Rome, Italy), University of Lund (Lund, Sweden), University of Linnaeus (Kalmar and Växjö, Sweden), Agape@S:t Thomas (Lund, Sweden).

Main Researcher, Global-ANSWER Project: Belén Morata-García de la Puerta, University of Granada.

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Scientific programme of social work international conferences

Introduction

The present deliverable, entitled “Scientific Programme of Social Work D6.3 WP6 – UNIFI Report Public International Conferences”, drafted under the coordination of the University of Florence as lead partner, serves as the guide that has directed the scientific and public dissemination of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER - H2020 - MSCA-RISE-GA-872209). Although the University of Florence is the lead partner of this deliverable, it is essential to emphasise that this document is the result of close and fruitful collaboration among members of several project partners. The working group that contributed to its preparation was composed of several members of the University of Florence and one member from each of the other project partners: Ivana Acocella, Costanza Gasparo, Silvia Pezzoli and Annalisa Tonarelli (University of Florence), Francesca Rizzuto (University of Palermo), Laura María Zanón Bayón-Torres (Comillas Pontifical University), Paula Rodríguez Aznar (University of Granada) and Teres Hjärpe (Lund University). This synergy among the various partner institutions enriched the dissemination programme, ensuring a plurality of perspectives and an integrated approach to the complex themes of migration and social work.

The primary objective of this document is to illustrate in an organic way the strategies, selected events, and decisions made regarding the participation of the project’s Global-ANSWER network, over the course of four years (from 2022 to 2025), in major academic and training events, both at the national and international levels.

These activities fall within Work Package 6 (WP6), entirely dedicated to the dissemination of good practices in social work and human mobility. Their purpose is twofold: on the one hand, the widespread sharing of the results achieved by the project; on the other, the promotion of deep scientific and professional dialogue on the crucial issues addressed, with particular attention to topics related to migration, social inclusion, and the professionalisation of interventions in the sector.

The central goal was to present and discuss the project’s interim and final results with the global scientific community. This interaction created valuable opportunities for exchange and methodological comparison, which were fundamental for the validation of the good practices identified.

The dissemination plan included a wide range of conferences and scientific events, held both in Europe (within and beyond EU borders, as in the case of participation in Albania) and in all the project partner countries (Italy, Spain, and Sweden). This widespread geographical presence was strategic for expanding the network of stakeholders and fostering broader transnational dissemination of the results.

A distinctive element of this strategy was the joint participation of several project partners in the events. This approach strengthened interdisciplinary collaboration and promoted direct exchanges of experiences and expertise, contributing to the construction of a coherent and shared narrative of the project, capable of highlighting the local and disciplinary specificities of each actor. The variety of conferences selected, ranging from social work to sociology, from law to communication sciences, faithfully reflects the multidisciplinary composition of the project team. This structure allowed for a complex and multifaceted approach to migration phenomena, adopting a plurality of perspectives that represented a deliberate epistemological and organizational choice.

Particularly significant was the conception of dissemination as an opportunity for scientific co-construction. Conferences, seminars, summer schools, and public events were not seen merely as showcases to present results, but as privileged spaces to test hypotheses, evaluate tools and approaches, and engage with colleagues from diverse national and disciplinary contexts. This intense exchange actively contributed to the shared definition of good practices in the fields of social work and human mobility, making dissemination an active phase of the scientific process, capable of stimulating theoretical reflections and challenging key concepts such as social innovation, inclusion, and governance.

The interdisciplinary nature of the project was consistently reflected in the dissemination activities. The project did not confine itself to a single theoretical framework but opened itself to engagement with heterogeneous fields such as the sociology of migration, law and human rights, educational sciences, public policy studies, and political communication. This openness made dissemination a true representation of the complexity that characterizes the project itself, translating its theoretical and methodological richness into acts of communication and dialogue that amplified its impact.

Social work international conference planned in the Project

During the implementation of the project, the original plan for conference participation was partially reorganized. However, it is important to highlight the four international conferences for which the presence of the Global-ANSWER team was planned from the outset of the project:

- The International Social Work Conference
- The European Association of Schools of Social Work
- The Ibero-American Conference of Social Work and Social Services
- The International Conference of Migrations in Andalusia
- The new panel “Social Work and Human Mobility”, promoted by Global-ANSWER.

The changes to the original plan were driven both by logistical reasons, such as the fact that some conferences were not rescheduled during the project years, and by a strategic decision to open up to new thematic areas and consciously opt for alternative events, in order to explore additional thematic dimensions of the project while maintaining consistency with its scientific and operational objectives. This adaptation process, far from representing a weakness, demonstrated the team’s ability to manage dissemination flexibly and resiliently, ensuring continuity and coherence in the project’s visibility. Regarding the originally planned conferences:

- The joint participation of the University of Granada and the University of Palermo in the **International Social Work Conference (CIFETS)**, held from 17 to 19 April 2024. This event, like many others, was held in person, allowing for direct and in-depth discussion. Two contributions were presented, focusing respectively on the participatory construction of good practices and on social innovation in social work with migrants.
- The University of Florence participated in the **European Conference on Social Work Education (ECSWE)**, held in Salzburg from 23 to 26 June 2025. In this case as well, participation was in person, with the presentation of a paper focused on building an integrated governance model for the reception and integration of asylum seekers, with a focus on the role of social work professionals in such projects.
- In place of the **Ibero-American Conference of Social Work and Social Services** and **International Conference of Migrations in Andalusia**, organized by the Institute for Migration Research (University of Granada), participation was directed to the **Migration**

Studies Ph.D. Summer School (MISSCHO), also organized by the Institute for Migration Research in 2023 (3–6 July) and 2024 (8–11 July). This Summer School, with the active contribution of partners from the University of Palermo and Lund University, focused in 2023 on “Representation, narratives and discourse on migration” and in 2024 on “Migration in the digital era: challenging theory, methods and practice” combining in-person sessions with online platforms to enable broader and more diverse participation.

- The **new panel “Social Work and Human Mobility”**, promoted by Global-ANSWER was developed in the **X Congreso de la Red Española de Política Social (REPS)**, held from 22 to 24 October 2025 in La Rioja, where a thematic panel entitled “Buenas prácticas y movilidad humana: un enfoque innovador para la inclusión y la protección social” was promoted in person and online on behalf of the Global-ANSWER project. The panel falls under Task 6.2 of WP5, entitled “Research dissemination of good practices in social work and human mobility” and represents the central and most relevant panel for the dissemination of the project, aimed at sharing and spreading research activities and results, including the social innovation model developed by the Global-ANSWER network.

In addition to these conferences, the Global-ANSWER team participated in and organized other conferences, workshops, and seminars. Dissemination was thus constructed as a tool in the service of the project’s growth, acting on multiple fronts simultaneously. On one hand, it targeted the international academic community, aiming to build lasting relationships and influence research agendas. On the other hand, it also included a training, outreach, and local dimension, through seminars, summer schools, and public meetings with social workers, policymakers, and third-sector actors. This dual approach generated differentiated and multi-level impacts, helping to transfer the knowledge produced into concrete action and fostering processes of social change.

National and international conferences. Topics

Category 1 – Definition and dissemination of good practices in social work and human mobility

This group of abstracts focuses on the analysis, identification, and promotion of innovative and transferable methodologies, models, and strategies capable of effectively addressing the challenges posed by contemporary migration and social inclusion. At the core of this category is a systematic reflection on the definition of “good practices” and some of their key characteristics to be identified and explored: the coherence between the design of interventions and the objectives pursued; awareness and reflexivity in implementation and monitoring; the sustainability and transferability of the solutions developed; inclusiveness and attention to intersectional approaches, ensuring participation and non-discrimination of all stakeholders involved. Understood in this way, good practices not only expand scientific knowledge but also have significant impacts on the improvement of professional practice and the effectiveness of public policies.

Through comparative studies on local governments and social work practices, significant differences emerge linked to political-institutional contexts, service networks, and migrant integration policies. Territorial analysis of practices—such as those observed in the reception and integration systems in Italy and Spain—provides concrete examples of replicable pathways that place multi-stakeholder collaboration and shared governance of migration policies at the centre. Another common thread among the abstracts in this category is the reflection on the concept of social innovation, useful for understanding the dynamism of social work practices. Innovation, in fact, is not limited to the mere replication of existing models but is realized through the co-construction of effective solutions via collaboration among institutions, professionals, researchers, and migrant communities.

The abstracts highlight how multidisciplinary dialogue and international exchange lay the foundations for promoting continuous professional development and encouraging the dissemination of operational tools grounded in research, experience, and inter-contextual knowledge transfer.

Key concepts defining this category:

- Collaborative construction of a definition of good practices
- Social innovation and human mobility

- SAI Palermo as a good practice
- Global Social Work: overall project framework
- Training cycles and seminars connected to the dissemination of good practices

Abstracts included in this category:

- *Approches internationales des recherches universitaires sur le travail social. La place spécifique des enseignants-chercheurs comme médiateur du décloisonnement des savoirs*
- *Cycle of meetings on analysis and practices of social service*
- *Cycle of meetings on social service and intervention in support of the family in Spain*
- *Disabilità e migrazioni: diseguaglianze nell'accesso alla cura*
- *Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (I jornada)*
- *Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (II jornada)*
- *Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (III jornada internacionales)*
- *Final del proyecto Global-Answer "Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region"*
- *From "lost" to "productive" time in the reception system: Challenges for the forced migrant's right to study and lifelong learning*
- *Hacia la construcción colaborativa de una definición de buenas prácticas en el ámbito del trabajo social y la movilidad humana*
- *I seminario: acompañamiento a adultos y menores de origen extranjero. Una reflexión desde la práctica profesional*
- *Il benessere organizzativo nel sistema di accoglienza: Prospettive degli assistenti sociali dal progetto H2020 Global-ANSWER*
- *Movilidades humanas. Buenas prácticas para proteger en la desprotección*
- *Panel "Buenas prácticas y movilidad humana: un enfoque innovador para la inclusión y la protección social"*
- *The enclosures and sadness of migrant categories*

- *The institutional logics and the classification processes of gender-based violence (GBV): Categorizations of provisions accessed by migrant women having a precarious legal status within secondary welfare provisions in Italy and Sweden*
- *Una reflexión teórica del concepto de innovación social y su operacionalización en el campo del trabajo social y la movilidad humana*

Category 2 – Local governance and territorial reception models (Tuscany and Andalusia)

The collection of abstracts grouped under the category *Local Governance and Territorial Reception Models (Tuscany and Andalusia)* stands out for its ability to offer a comparative perspective on reception structures and the relationships between public administrations and the third sector in the two regional contexts, highlighting the relevance of regulatory-institutional frameworks and different political and social processes. In the comparison between Tuscany and Andalusia, two distinct institutional and operational arrangements emerge: Tuscany is characterized by a decentralized and widespread system involving municipalities, unions of municipalities and local health authorities, while in Andalusia the system is more centralized at the state level, with NGOs managing reception centres at the local level.

The abstracts emphasize the central importance of the Reception and Integration System (SAI) in Tuscany, underlining the strategic role of social work not only as a link between beneficiaries and services but also as a promoter of innovative integration practices, fostering coordination between social, health, and associative dimensions. In the Andalusian region, particular attention is paid to the specific vulnerabilities of migrants, especially regarding access to housing, which is considered a fundamental right in the processes of autonomy.

The works also explore the area of labor inclusion, addressing common difficulties such as language barriers and the non-recognition of qualifications, and highlighting synergies built between public administrations, businesses, training agencies, and the third sector. This focus on collaborative networks, both during reception and in support of housing and employment autonomy, runs through all the abstracts, providing an updated and concrete portrait of operational systems, policies, and challenges shaping migrant inclusion pathways in the two regional contexts.

The entire body of abstracts offers a multifaceted reading of local and regional strategies, showing how the effectiveness of the solutions adopted

depends on the capacity for cooperation among different actors, the strength of territorial networks, and the ability to translate normative and programmatic principles into effective and sustainable practices. Taken together, the contributions provide a framework that allows for recognizing both differences and strengths in regional models and can serve as a starting point for reflections useful to the future of reception and inclusion governance in Europe.

Key concepts defining this category:

- Reception and reception systems in Tuscany and Andalusia
- Collaborative governance and SAI models (municipalities, unions, Health Societies)
- Institutional discourse on rights and social services
- Politicization of migration: the Andalusian case
- Access to housing and housing policies

Abstracts included in this category:

- *Cycle of meetings on social service and intervention in support of the family in Spain*
- *Empadronamiento e Arraigo in Spagna: il contributo del Servizio de Atención al Inmigrante (SAI) del Comune di Granada*
- *International social work on the field 2024 | Seminars series*
- *L'accoglienza e la presa in carico di soggetti vulnerabili nel Circondario dell'Empolese Valdelsa*
- *Legalità precaria del migrante in Italia. Evoluzione nel sistema normativo*
- *Panel "Human mobility in social services: Insights from the Global ANSWER project"*
- *Pratiche del lavoro sociale nel sistema di accoglienza ed integrazione*
- *Riflessioni a partire dal testo: From the 'White Paper' of the Tuscany region to replicable best practices*
- *The creation of an integrated governance model for reception and integration measures for asylum seekers and refugees: The role of social workers in SAI projects in the Tuscany region*

Category 3 – Rights, vulnerability and social inclusion

This section addresses the structural and regulatory barriers—education, employment, and housing—that hinder migrants’, refugees’, and asylum seekers’ access to fundamental rights. Alongside these obstacles, cultural barriers are also highlighted as elements that reproduce discrimination and inequality. The right to education is frequently discussed as a means of repairing biographical fractures, with particular attention to the role of universities in fostering human rights protection within a framework of equity and social justice.

At the same time, the abstracts highlight contradictions within European asylum policies and reception systems, which often transform migrants from historical-political subjects into objects of care. These systems are marked by ambiguity, oscillating between charitable interventions and mechanisms of control, with repercussions on national and local administrative practices that are frequently restrictive and inconsistent. Legal status emerges as a further discriminatory factor, contributing to the fragmentation of rights and reinforcing forms of social exclusion.

Some contributions adopt a territorial perspective, examining urban districts marked by strong migratory presence to explore processes of transformation, borders, and multiculturalism, and to question whether the coexistence of different groups leads to genuine exchange or mere parallelism. Others focus on the ambivalences of national regulatory frameworks, particularly regarding the entry and residence of foreign workers, tracing the shift from more inclusive approaches to increasingly restrictive measures.

Housing is addressed as a crucial issue, interpreted not only as a denied right but also as a symbolic and material space of inclusion or marginalization. Access to housing—frequently constrained by regulation, discriminatory practices, and market dynamics—becomes a test of the quality of urban integration. Within this framework, the notion of the inclusive city acquires centrality, both as a policy goal and as a collective process aimed at ensuring equal access to services, mobility, participation, and active citizenship.

Finally, local and academic experiences are discussed as examples of innovative practices designed to move beyond the reduction of migrants to passive beneficiaries, instead recognizing and enhancing their transformative potential through education, socio-labour empowerment, and the co-design of urban spaces.

Key concepts defining this category:

- Right to education and lifelong learning

- Labour inclusion
- Precarious legality in Italy
- Empadronamiento and Arraigo in Spain
- Access to housing and denied rights

Abstracts included in this category:

- *I seminario: acompañamiento a adultos y menores de origen extranjero. Una reflexión desde la práctica profesional*
- *Cycle of meetings on analysis and practices of social service*
- *Cycle of meetings on social service and intervention in support of the family in Spain*
- *Coloquios sobre investigación en Trabajo Social*
- *Disabilità e migrazioni: diseguglianze nell'accesso alla cura*
- *Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (I jornada)*
- *Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (II jornada)*
- *Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (III jornada internacionales)*
- *Final del proyecto Global-Answer "Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region"*
- *From "lost" to "productive" time in the reception system: Challenges for the forced migrant's right to study and lifelong learning*
- *Il benessere organizzativo nel sistema di accoglienza: Prospettive degli assistenti sociali dal progetto H2020 Global-ANSWER*
- *The enclosures and sadness of migrant categories*
- *The institutional logics and the classification processes of gender-based violence (GBV): Categorizations of provisions accessed by migrant women having a precarious legal status within secondary welfare provisions in Italy and Sweden*

Category 4 – Gender, violence and intersectionality

The analysis of migrant women's experiences highlights the need for an intersectional approach capable of connecting gender, legal status, ethnicity, and social class. Migration does not only produce geographic mobility but also specific vulnerabilities that intersect with border regimes and institutional logics. Migrant women with precarious status face multiple forms of violence: gender-based violence, violence linked to legal precarity, and violence associated with structural discrimination (racism, Islamophobia, xenophobia). In this context, violence should not be interpreted solely as interpersonal phenomena but also as expressions of power structures operating at national and transnational levels.

Intersectional feminist literature has shown how systems of oppression operate simultaneously and interdependently. This approach allows for understanding the experiences of migrant women not as exceptions but as an integral part of the limitations and contradictions of European welfare systems. In contexts such as Italy and Sweden, difficulties in accessing welfare for migrant women with precarious status arise not only from bureaucratic and legal constraints but also from cultural representations and stereotypes that place them in marginalized positions. Here, secondary welfare actors—NGOs, religious associations, volunteer organizations—play a crucial supplementary role, but their action also highlights the structural inadequacy of public systems.

The intersection between Islamophobia and gender represents another critical area. In Spain, for example, Muslim women are at the center of a public discourse that tends to reduce their subjectivity to symbols of backwardness or radicalization. This dynamic is visible both in security policies (such as school protocols for preventing radicalization) and in some strands of mainstream feminism, which interpret the veil as a sign of oppression without considering the voices and agency of the women themselves. Adopting an intersectional feminist approach, however, allows for recognizing how oppressions accumulate and transform in different contexts, and how migrant women develop strategies of resistance, solidarity, and self-organization.

From this perspective, processes of violence and marginalization must be understood not only in terms of vulnerability but also as spaces for political action and social transformation. Migrant women's practices of resistance—from cultural activism to civic participation—demonstrate the capacity to redefine welfare boundaries and introduce new forms of social justice. The study of intersections between gender, violence, and migration status thus

enables not only understanding existing inequalities but also imagining inclusive welfare models that genuinely address plural subjectivities.

Following this thread, the abstracts included in this category address the multiple inequalities experienced by migrant women, particularly those with precarious status. They explore how institutional logics and border regimes influence access to services and protection from gender-based violence. The focus is placed on the action of secondary welfare actors (NGOs, religious institutions, volunteer organizations), who compensate for the shortcomings of official systems. Critical approaches inspired by intersectional feminism and social justice emerge throughout.

Key concepts defining this category:

- Gender-based violence and access to welfare in Italy and Sweden
- Islamophobia and structural racism in Spain
- Role of intersectionality and critical feminism

Abstracts included in this category:

- *Islamophobia in Spain and Europe*
- *The institutional logics and the classification processes of gender-based violence (GBV): Categorizations of provisions accessed by migrant women having a precarious legal status within secondary welfare provisions in Italy and Sweden*

Category 5 – Cities, urban space and memory

The analysis of migration in urban contexts requires moving beyond a purely demographic or socio-economic perspective and integrating conceptual tools that can connect spatial materiality, everyday practices, and social memory. The city is a field of spatial, symbolic, and institutional forces that defines access, exclusion, and possibilities for recognition. The concept of the *right to the city* (Lefebvre) offers a political lens to interpret migrants' spatial claims as emerging forms of citizenship; it is not only about access to services or housing but also about rights to the collective production of urban space. This theoretical reference helps to understand how urban policies shape the material and symbolic possibilities for migrants to inhabit the city in a recognized way.

From this perspective, social memory and public history practices constitute the symbolic side of urban space construction; migrants' personal stories, neighbourhood memories, and forgotten places contribute to the production of a plural urban heritage. Through oral memory archives, the musealization of migration, or artistic practices, historical knowledge is produced that reconfigures public perception of neighbourhoods and can foster forms of recognition and legitimacy. In parallel, placemaking practices—such as markets, places of worship, ethnic shops, and cultural events—transform public and commercial spaces, creating social networks and strengthening the sense of belonging. These processes enhance integration possibilities but can also generate conflicts in the presence of gentrification dynamics or exclusive regulation of public space.

In this sense, integration processes must be understood as multi-level and non-linear, simultaneously encompassing residential, economic, cultural, and civic dimensions. Such perspectives require a redefinition of integration policies, which must include not only economic and housing measures but also recognition of migrants as co-producers of urban space and collective memory.

Paying attention to this important dimension, the abstracts included in this category reflect on the relationship between migration and urban transformations, observing how migrants shape urban space through memory, public history, and everyday practices. A critical approach is thus proposed, valuing migrants' subjective narratives and promoting inclusive and participatory cities, inspired by the concept of the *right to the city*. However, urban segregation, gentrification, and symbolic boundaries separating old and new waves of migration are also analyzed.

Key concepts defining this category:

- “Voices from the City”: public history and immigration
- Right to the city and urban barriers
- Usera neighbourhood in Madrid: identity, boundaries and multiculturalism

Abstracts included in this category:

- *The Right to the city and migration: barriers, practices and imaginaries*
- *Usera between urban transformations, borders and multiculturalism*
- *Public history, cities and immigration*

Category 6 – Categories, languages, social critics and communication

The abstracts in this category offer a critical reflection on the institutional and academic languages that contribute to the construction of stigmatizing categories for migrants. They denounce the “sad” and immobilizing nature of certain labels—such as “refugee”, “illegal immigrant” and “applicant”—and call for new emancipatory narratives. The approach draws inspiration from post-humanist thought and the philosophy of difference (Braidotti), emphasizing the need for symbolic resistance and collective imagination. Some studies have proposed critiques of institutional semantics and categories that define human mobility in reductive or pathologizing terms, also analyzing them through media coverage of migration phenomena in countries such as Italy and Spain.

In some cases, attention is focused on information practices that otherize migrants and on the discursive modes used in journalistic narratives, which primarily result in the spectacular and personalizing dramatization of the migration phenomenon and a substantial trivialization of the causes and specificities related to the countries of origin. The role of journalism in the perception of the Other-Migrant emerges as one of the central issues of the democratic debate, because the mediated description of the migratory phenomenon influences public opinion and offers a daily pervasive construction of the Other. This process has significant political and social consequences, since the journalistic construction of reality influences individual perceptions and behaviours. Some cases of media representation strategies were analyzed: fragmentation, depersonalization, decontextualization, and, above all, the presence of a Western point of view that produces a biased mirror of migration, where the “Other” is usually presented as a cause of problems.

Key concepts defining this category:

- Institutional languages and symbolic resistances
- Migrants’ news coverage

Abstracts included in this category

- *Newsmedia representation of migrants in Italy. Trends and perspectives*
- *The enclosures and sadness of migrant categories*
- *Tra crisi ed emergenza. L’evoluzione dei discorsi politici, giuridici e giornalistici sulle migrazioni in Toscana tra concordanze e divergenze*

Category 7 – Training, exchange and dissemination

During the project (from 2022 to 2025), all partners organized and implemented numerous training events, international seminars, summer schools, and workshops with the aim of promoting dialogue among universities, professionals, and activists. Research findings were also disseminated through participation in international conferences and lectures by professors and researchers involved in Global Answer.

This section presents abstracts from the numerous training and transnational exchange initiatives, promoted by the project partners: seminar series, training days for cultural mediators, summer schools, and public events were designed and configured as spaces for exchange between research and practice. For example, a relevant issue of the project was the analysis of tools and practices of Social Service; some seminars and meetings were organized to understand social work methodologies and promote knowledge exchange between local and international experts in the field. The most significant outcome of these initiatives was the initiation of an ongoing process of building and strengthening an international epistemic community, capable of proposing updates to the operational tools of social work from an intercultural, participatory, and transdisciplinary perspective.

Key concepts defining this category:

- International seminars
- Summer schools
- Training days for cultural mediators
- Meetings on social work and interventions on families

Abstracts included in this category:

- *Border crossing*
- *Cycle of meetings on analysis and practices of social service*
- *Cycle of meetings on social service and intervention in support of the family in Spain*
- *Giornate di formazione per mediatori culturali*
- *Human mobility: best practices in a context of precarity and expulsions*
- *International social work on the field 2024 | International seminars*

- *Newsmedia representation of migrants in Italy. Trends and perspectives*
- *Políticas de inclusión social en Europa. Perspectivas comparadas sobre la acogida y acompañamiento de personas solicitantes de protección internacional*

Document structure

Each activity was carefully documented through two main sections. The first focused on the technical information related to the event: title, dates, location, participants, keywords, references, logos, and funding acknowledgments; the second concentrated on the scientific content, presenting the topics addressed, the objectives of participation, and the results shared. This tracking system ensured transparency and consistency throughout the dissemination process, contributing to consolidating the visibility and scientific authority of the project.

INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR

International seminar

Cycle of meetings on analysis and practices of social service

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Observation of workspaces in the field of social service

Annick Magnier (University of Florence)

Patricia Porcel and Rosa M^a Pérez López (Social Workers of the Municipality of Granada)

Indicators of housing poverty

Annick Magnier and Sandro Landucci (University of Florence)

Patricia Porcel and Rosa M^a Pérez López (Social workers of the Municipality of Granada)

University of Florence, October 11-25, 2022

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/1-Ciclo%20di%20incontri%20su%20analisi%20e%20pratiche%20de%20servizio%20sociale.pdf>

Abstract

This training cycle, conducted as part of the Urban Sociology course activities and within the framework of the course “Analisi Territoriale per la Progettazione Sociale”, Master’s Degree in Design and Management of Social Interventions (University of Florence), focuses on social work tools. The seminars are organized with the participation of the international team from the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209). The initiative aims to provide an in-depth understanding of social work methodologies, promoting knowledge exchange between local and international experts in the field. The sessions will address key aspects of social work in urban contexts, fostering a collaborative learning environment for both students and professionals.

Keywords: Social work; Urban sociology; Training; Global-ANSWER project

International seminar

Public history, cities and immigration

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Voices from the city: public history and immigration

Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence)

University of Florence, October 25, 2023

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/2-Public%20history%2C%20city%20and%20immigration.pdf>

Abstract

The lesson *Voices from the city: public history and immigration* explore how the personal stories of immigrants contribute to the collective narrative of cities, transforming urban spaces into places of shared memory. Through public history, these often-marginalized voices are brought to the forefront, offering new perspectives on the past and fostering intercultural dialogue in the present. The lesson is organized within the framework of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), and takes place during “Public History”, part of the Bachelor's Degree in Political Science at the University of Florence.

Keywords: Public history; Immigration; Shared memory; Intercultural dialogue

International seminar

Coloquios sobre investigación en Trabajo Social

(Dialogues on research in Social Work)

External initiative within the Global-ANSWER network involving members of the project team

Trabajo social y migraciones (*Social work and migration*)

Presentación (Presentation)

Francisco Ródenas (Auets)

Laura Zanón (Pontifical University Comillas)

Violeta Quiroga (Auets)

Ponencia marco (*Keynote presentation*)

El trabajo social en el contexto de la movilidad humana (Social work in the context of human mobility)

Laura Zanón (Pontifical University Comillas)

Mesa de investigación aplicada (*Applied research panel*)

Presentación (Presentation)

Almudena Juárez (Pontifical University Comillas)

Presentación del proyecto "The Global-ANSWER network, trabajo social y movilidad humana" (Presentation of the project "The Global-answer network: social work and human mobility")

Belén Morata (University of Granada)

Cuestiones éticas de la investigación en Trabajo social y movilidad humana (Ethical issues in research on social work and human mobility)

Teresa Díaz (University of Granada)

Debate (Debate)

Almudena Juárez (Pontifical University Comillas)

Clausura (Closing)

Violeta Quiroga (University of Barcelona)

Online, April 18, 2023

Link to the seminar:

https://auets.es/images/COLOQUIO_9_PROGRAMA.pdf

Abstract

The Congress focused on analysing the role of social work in the context of human mobility, addressing the challenges that current migration processes pose to traditional intervention methodologies. It emphasized the need to incorporate intercultural, transnational, and human rights-based approaches to ensure the inclusion, dignity, and protection of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers. As part of the event, the Global-ANSWER project, funded by the European Union was presented. This project involves academic institutions, public administrations, and social organizations from Spain, Italy and Sweden and aims to conduct a comparative study of good practices in social work and social services across the Euro-Mediterranean region. Its objective is to strengthen local capacities in supporting vulnerable populations by promoting more inclusive, participatory, and rights-based social policies. The congress also addressed key ethical dilemmas in research involving migrant populations, such as informed consent, the accurate representation of their voices, and the protection of sensitive data. The importance of adopting respectful and engaged methodological approaches was underscored approaches that not only enable a deeper understanding of social realities but also actively contribute to their transformation, in alignment with the ethical principles of social work and the core values of the European Union. Members of the project “Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region” (Global-ANSWER-H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209) participated in the seminar.

Keywords: Human mobility; Social work; Intercultural and rights-based approaches; Migration and inclusion; Ethical research with migrant populations

International seminar

Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (I jornada)

(Research experiences in social work with migrants - Seminar 1)

Beneficios para ampliar el conocimiento, para la práctica profesional y las políticas públicas *(Benefits for expanding knowledge, professional practice and public policies)*

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the euromediterranean region

Ana Huesca (Pontifical University Comillas)

La inconstitucionalidad (parcial) de la nueva ley francesa de inmigración. La debida observancia del procedimiento legislativo como causa principal *(The (partial) unconstitutionality of the new french immigration law: proper observance of the legislative procedure as the main cause)*

Isabella Maria Lo Presti (University of Palermo)

Derecho de las personas y las relaciones familiares en situaciones de vulnerabilidad *(Rights of individuals and family relationships in situations of vulnerability)*

Lalage Mormile (University of Palermo)

“WE PROPOSE - Processes, policies and networks in support of women’s returnees to Tunisia and Morocco”

Umberto Di Maggio (LUMSA University, Rome)

Investigar para realizar acompañamientos desde el enfoque de derechos con personas migrantes *(Research to carry out accompaniment from a rights-based approach with migrants)*

Lucía López López (Red Acoge)

Online, March 4, 2024

Link to the seminar:

<https://eventos.comillas.edu/112412/detail/experiencias-de-investigacion-en-trabajo-social-sobre-personas-migrantes-.html>

Abstract

This session addresses different issues related to research about migrants from the perspective of social work. In this sense, from different disciplines such as sociology or law, topics are presented that are transversal both for understanding migration and for research in Social Work. Aspects such as family relationships, administrative procedures, public policies and their impact on migrant groups, as well as the importance of research to carry out an intervention based on a rights-based approach are issues that are addressed in this session. This seminar is part of the project “Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region” (Global-ANSWER-H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209)

Keywords: Migration; Social work; Public policies; Rights-based approach

International seminar

Políticas de inclusión social en Europa. Perspectivas comparadas sobre la acogida y acompañamiento de personas solicitantes de protección internacional

(Social inclusion policies in Europe: comparative perspectives on the reception and support of international protection seekers)

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Welcome

M. Belén Morata García de la Puerta (University of Granada)

Medidas penales para combatir la victimización de migrantes: La política criminal española y la necesidad de homogeneizar un corpus iuris europeo (*Criminal measures to combat the victimization of migrants: Spanish criminal policy and the need to standardize a European corpus iuris*)

Carlos Aránguez Sánchez (University of Granada)

Desafíos y oportunidades en la atención a personas solicitantes de protección internacional en Europa (*Challenges and opportunities in the care of international protection applicants in Europe*)

Daria Mendola (University of Palermo)

Ignazia Bartholini (University of Palermo)

Sonia Sahli (Asociación Engranajes)

Belén Arranz (Diversidades Acoge)

Maria Nella Uppi (OXFAM Italy)

Andrea Botazzi (OXFAM Italy)

Giulia Salvini (OXFAM Italy)

Zanobi Tosi (OXFAM Italy)

Sabina Morosini (OXFAM Italy)

Moderator: María Teresa Gijón Sánchez

University of Granada, March 15, 2024

Link to the seminar:

<https://proyectos.ugr.es/global-answer/information/news/global-answer-team-evaluates-reception-and-inclusion-policies>

Abstract

The seminar opens with an address by the principal investigator of the project, Professor Belén Morata, who welcomes all attendees and provides an overview of the project “Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), which focuses on comparative studies of international mobility. This project stands as one of the key initiatives in the field of Social Work, supported and funded by the European Union (European Commission H2020). The first presentation is delivered by Carlos Aránguez Sánchez, Professor of Criminal Law at the University of Granada and one of the leading practicing lawyers in the city dedicated to this area of study and practice. Aránguez discusses the penal measures used to address the victimization of migrants, with a focus on Spanish criminal policy and the need to standardize a *European corpus iuris*—a unified legal framework across the EU. After a short break, the morning session continues with analysis, reflection, and debate through a roundtable discussion on the challenges and opportunities in assisting individuals seeking international protection in Europe. The forum brings together experts from universities, institutions, and organizations specializing in migrant protection. Participants include Daria Mendola and Ignazia Bartholini from the University of Palermo (Italy), along with representatives from local organizations such as Sonia Sahli from the Engranajes Association (Granada) and Belén Arranz from Diversidades Acolle (Vigo). Representatives from OXFAM Italy—including Maria Nella Lippi, Andrea Botazzi, Giulia Salvini, Zanobi Tosi, and Sabina Morosini—also join the discussion. The seminar concludes with a reflection on the challenges and opportunities posed by mobility and migration within the European Union, with particular attention to Spain and Italy as especially sensitive and strategic regions due to their geographical position as key entry points.

Keywords: Migration; International mobility; Social work; International protection; European Union

International seminar

International social work on the field 2024 | International seminars

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Migrant woman: inclusion pathways in Spain and in Italy

Belén Arranz (Diversities Vigo)

Maria Chiara Monti (Centre Penc)

Border Violence and memory practices in the Mediterranean

Silvia Di Meo (University of Palermo)

Immigration in Spain, beyond the data: troubles and challenges

Antonio Eito Mateo (University of Zaragoza)

Social work under impact from a restrictive Swedish migration policy

Jesper Johansson & Kristina Gustafsson (University of Linnaeus)

Climate change and migration

Angelika Kaffrell Lindahl (University of Midsweden)

Unaccompanied minors in Greece and Italy: an exploration of the challenges for social Work within tighter immigration and resource constraints

Ravinder Barn (Royal Holloway University of London)

University of Palermo, March 21–May 29, 2024

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/cultureesocieta/.content/documenti/Locandina-International-Seminars-Social-Work-on-the-field-2024.pdf>

Abstract

As part of the course “International Social Work: Global Issues in Migration and Development”, taught by Professor Roberta Di Rosa within the Master’s Degree Program in Cooperation, Development and Migrations (LM-81), an international series of public seminars—held both in person and online—will offer students the opportunity to engage with leading international experts in the field of migration. The initiative also highlights the presence in Palermo of scholars from partner institutions participating in the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: International Social Work; Global-ANSWER; Development; Migration; Social work

International seminar

Giornate di formazione per mediatori culturali

Initiative organized by prof. Mette Rudvin and the Global-ANSWER network

Teoria e pratica della mediazione culturale (*Theory and practice of cultural mediation*)

University of Palermo, May 10, 2024

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/cultureesocieta/.content/documenti/Teoria-e-Pratica-della-Mediazione-Culturale-Tavola-Rotonda.pdf>

Giornate di formazione per mediatori culturali. Approfondire le conoscenze teoriche e pratiche della mediazione culturale (*Training days for cultural mediators. deepening theoretical and practical knowledge of cultural mediation*)

University of Palermo, May 10-11, 2024

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/cultureesocieta/.content/documenti/Teoria-e-Pratica-della-Mediazione-Culturale-Workshop.pdf>

Abstract

As part of the activities of the H2020 Global-ANSWER project, coordinated by Professor Roberta T. Di Rosa, two training days for cultural mediators will be held, organized by Professor Mette Rudvin. The sessions will feature contributions from international researchers and experts who will engage in dialogue with local academics and professionals. Cultural mediators from the FAMI COOPERA project—carried out in 2023 in collaboration with the Municipality of Palermo—will also take part in the discussion. The initiative also highlights the presence in Palermo of representatives from partner institutions participating in the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: International Social work; Global-ANSWER; Development; Migration; Social work; Cultures

International seminar

Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (II jornada)

(Research experiences in social work with migrants (Seminar 2))

Tuscany and immigration: replicable best practice

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence)

Sheyla Moroni (University of Florence)

Amudena Juárez (Pontifical University Comillas)

Lucía López (Red Acoge)

Pontifical University Comillas, September 25, 2024

Link to the seminar:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1x0mntB6j17lnS35482aifGdcf177onle/view?usp=sharing>

Abstract

This presentation explores the reception and integration of migrants in Tuscany, with a focus on identifying and analysing replicable good practices. It examines the evolution of immigration and asylum policies in Italy, highlighting the shift towards a multi-level governance framework and the crucial role of the third sector in integration efforts. The presentation also highlights specific projects and initiatives in Tuscany that address various aspects of migrant integration, including healthcare, social assistance, intercultural mediation, legal assistance, language learning, employment inclusion, social cohesion and housing autonomy. This paper is presented within the framework of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209). In particular, it focuses on Case Studies 8 and 9 from the University of Florence, titled “Comparative Case Studies on the Regional Reception Systems for Migrants in Tuscany and Andalusia”.

Keywords: Human mobility; Social work; Good practices; Integration

International seminar

Border crossing

External initiative within the Global-ANSWER network involving members of the project team

Opening remarks

Serena Marcenò (University di Palermo)

Familias migrantes, identidad nacional y democracias sexual en los países europeos (*Migrant families, national identity and sexual democracies in European countries*)

Sandra Gil (University of Buenos Aires)

Subverting the border thinking and gaze: creative resistance in times of migration

Federica Mazzara (University of Westminster)

Climate change. Migration and co-social Justice

Angelika Kaffrell-Lindahl (Mid Sweden University)

Lebanon history and social inclusion of migrants in Spain. Reflections and proposal by Global Answer

Teresa Diaz Aznarte, M. Belén Morata García de la Puerta (University of Granada)

Being a project manager in an international NGO

Stefania Martello (Premiere Urgence International and Danish Refugee Council)

University of Palermo, October 28-31, 2024

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/cultureesocieta/.content/documenti/Locandina-Border-Crossing-Ciclo-di-Seminari-2024.pdf>

Abstract

The seminars are organized by the Master's Degree Program in Cooperation, Development and Migration at the University of Palermo, in collaboration with the scientific team of the Global - ANSWER Unit (UNIPA) and take place from October 28 to 31, 2024. Speakers include professors from various universities—Universidad de Buenos Aires, University of Westminster, Mid Sweden University, Universidad de Granada and UNIPA—who explore the topic of migration from diverse perspectives. Discussions address the links between migration and local conflicts (e.g., Lebanon and Gaza), the challenges faced by migrant families in different countries (such as Spain and Argentina) and the effects of climate change on migratory flows. Issues of social inclusion and migrant protection are also examined, with several proposals presented based on the initial findings of the Global ANSWER research. Members of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209) participated in the seminar.

Keywords: Migration; Social inclusion; Climate change; Local conflicts

International seminar

Cycle of meetings on social service and intervention in support of the family in Spain

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Community social services in family and child care in Spain

Sandra Lorena Martín Robles (Municipality of Granada) and Vicente Martín López (Municipality of Granada)

Equipos de Tratamiento familiar in Spain

Antonia Cobos Gámez (Municipality of Granada)

Social assistance for the elderly in Spain

María Teresa Elvira Arriaza (Municipality of Granada) and María Luisa Sola Morillas (Municipality of Granada)

The role of the social educator in the *Equipo de tratamiento familiar* of the Municipality of Granada

María Carmen Rivas Fernández (Municipality of Granada)

The role of the social worker in the *Equipo de tratamiento familiar* of the Municipality of Granada

Encarnación Gador Poza Pérez (Municipality of Granada)

University of Florence, February 25– April 10, 2025

Link to the seminar:

https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/3-Ciclo%20di%20incontri%20sul%20servizio%20sociale%20e%20l_intervento%20a%20supporto%20della%20famiglia%20in%20Spagna.pdf

Abstract

The training seminars on social work tools are organized within the framework of the Bachelor's Degree in Social Work and the Master's Degree in Social Intervention Design and Management at the University of Florence. These events feature contributions from the international team of the Global-ANSWER project, offering opportunities for exchange and in-depth exploration of practices and tools used in social work. The initiative is carried out with the participation of project members within the framework of "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Social work; Training seminars; Global-ANSWER; Intervention design

International seminar

L'accoglienza e la presa in carico di soggetti vulnerabili nel

Circondario dell'Empolese Valdelsa

(The reception and care of vulnerable individuals in the Empolese Valdelsa District)

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Saluti (*Welcome addresses*)

Alessio Mugnaini – President of the Union of the Empolese Valdelsa District
Francesca Gianni – President of SDSEW and Delegate of the Union for Social Policies and Immigration

Alessio Mantellassi – Mayor of the Municipality of Empoli, Delegate for Housing Policies

Agnese Granchi – Head of the Social and Socio-Assistential Services, Housing Policies and Immigration Department

Interventi (*Presentations*)

Struttura, organizzazione e funzioni del Servizio sociale e Socio-Assistenziale Territoriale della SDS Empolese Valdarno Valdelsa (*Structure, organization and functions of the Territorial Social and Socio-Assistential Service of the Empolese Valdarno Valdelsa Health and Welfare Society*)

Franco Doni - Director of the Empolese Valdarno Valdelsa Health and Welfare Society

Cittadini con background migratorio nel welfare locale: percorsi integrati di accoglienza e inclusione sociale (*Citizens with a migrant background in local welfare: integrated pathways of Reception and Social Inclusion*)

Francesca Cattaneo – IF Immigration, Empolese Valdarno Valdelsa Health and Welfare Society: Introduction and coordination of the presentations

Sabrina Loguercio – CO&SO, Cooperative *La Pietra d'Angolo*: Information points for foreign citizens

Chiara Dinucci – Coordinator ASEV: Linguistic and Cultural Mediation and Italian language (L2) courses

Unione dei Comuni Circondario dell'Empolese Valdelsa. La rete SAI (*Sistema Accoglienza Integrazione*) (*Union of Municipalities of the Empolese Valdelsa District - The SAI Network (Reception and Integration System)*)

Maurizio Cei – Coordinator of the SAI Project: From the national level to integration pathways within the local welfare system

Della rete internazionale di Global-ANSWER intervengono sul progetto (*Speakers from the international Global-ANSWER network present the project*):

M^a Carmen Rivas Fernández, M^a Luisa Sola Morillas, Encarnación Poza Pérez, and Sandra Lorena Martín Robles – Family Treatment Team, Municipality of Granada

Hajar Menssouri – Social Worker, Fundación Bayt Al-Thaqafa

Ivana Acocella and Carlo Baccetti – Department of Political and Social Sciences, University of Florence

Council Hall of the Municipality of Empoli, April 8, 2025

Link to the seminar:

[https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/Accoglienza%20e%20presa%20in%20carico%20di%20soggetti%20vulnerabili%20nel%20Circolario%20Empolese%20Valdelsa%20%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/Accoglienza%20e%20presa%20in%20carico%20di%20soggetti%20vulnerabili%20nel%20Circolario%20Empolese%20Valdelsa%20%20(1).pdf)

Abstract

The event explored the modalities of reception and integration of citizens with a migrant background within the local welfare system, highlighting the structures, functions, and operational networks of the Territorial Social and Socio-Assistive Service of the Empolese Valdarno Valdelsa. Following institutional greetings, the interventions presented concrete pathways for social inclusion, linguistic and cultural mediation, and informational services aimed at foreign citizens. The initiative promoted the exchange of good practices in reception and integration models, involving the SAI network (Reception and Integration System) of the Union of Municipalities of Empolese Valdelsa and the international Global-ANSWER network, with experts sharing family treatment approaches and intercultural welfare practices. The event was carried out within the framework of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), fostering exchange among social workers, local institutions, and migrant communities, and contributing to the dissemination of sustainable and inclusive integration models.

Keywords: Reception; Integration; Local welfare; Social inclusion

International seminar
Islamophobia in Spain and Europe

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Islamophobia in Spain: reality and public debate

Hajar Menssouri (Fundación Bayt Al Thaqafa and Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona)

University of Florence, April 14, 2025

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/Islamophobia%20in%20Spain%20and%20Europe.pdf>

Abstract

During the lesson, held as part of the course “Religioni e Relazioni Internazionali” within the Master's Degree in International Relations and European Studies (University of Florence), Islamophobia in Spain is examined as a form of structural racism deeply rooted in the country's colonial and imperial history. Islamophobia is discussed not only as anti-Muslim sentiment, but more specifically as anti-Maghrebi or anti-Moor sentiment, closely linked to the construction of national identity. A key focus of the lesson is the global political shift after 9/11, which contributes to the normalization and spread of Islamophobic discourse—not only among far-right groups but also across the broader political spectrum, including certain sectors of the left and feminist movements. In the Spanish context, the lesson explores the example of Catalonia, where security protocols such as PRODERAI are implemented. These measures, aimed at preventing radicalization, disproportionately target Muslim students and raise serious concerns about systemic discrimination. The lesson also includes a critical discussion of mainstream feminism, which often adopts Islamophobic positions—particularly in debates surrounding the hijab—while failing to apply an intersectional understanding of oppression that includes religion, race, and gender. This lesson is part of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Islamophobia; Structural racism; Spanish nationalism; Intersectional feminism; PRODERAI

International seminar

I seminario: acompañamiento a adultos y menores de origen extranjero. Una reflexión desde la práctica profesional.

(Seminar I: support for foreign adults and minors. A reflection based on professional practice)

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Chair:

Ana Huesca (Pontifical University Comillas)

Participants:

Patrizia Pappalardo (Municipality of Palermo) “Il Sistema di accoglienza e integrazione SAI e i minori stranieri non accompagnati” (*The SAI Reception and Integration System and unaccompanied foreign minors*)

Anna Rita di Cola (Municipality of Palermo) “Il Sistema di accoglienza e integrazione SAI Ordinari” (*The ordinary SAI Reception and Integration System*)

Inmaculada Ruiz-Fincias (Pontifical University Comillas) “Niños y jóvenes migrantes sin acompañamiento adulto en España: una realidad en constante cambio” (*Children and young migrants without adult accompaniment in Spain: a reality in constant change*)

Pontifical University Comillas, April 23, 2025

Link to the seminar:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1CGAxU6xASoLdtoYxYYZszC2ZNAbjfm1_/view?usp=sharing

Abstract

An ad-hoc seminar was organized at the University Comillas to reflect on an issue that currently worries the public: how to intervene with adult migrants in situations of exclusion, but above all how to adequately address the needs of unaccompanied minors of foreign origin who are located in southern Europe. Professor Inmaculada Fincas, from the University Comillas, delivered an in-depth presentation of this reality in Spain, describing the current situation and the challenges faced by social organisations and public administrations. From there, comparisons were drawn with the contributions of Patrizia Pappalardo and Anna Rita di Cola, both from the Municipality of Palermo. They presented the Italian reception and integration system for migrants, and specifically for unaccompanied minors, sharing some of the cases directly managed by the social services of Palermo. All of this took place within the framework of the project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), in which the participating institutions are members.

Keywords: Unaccompanied minors; Migrant integration; Social exclusion; Social work; Euro-Mediterranean cooperation

International seminar

The right to the city and migration: barriers, practices and imaginaries

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence)

University of Lund, May 21, 2025

Link to the seminar:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/The%20Right%20to%20the%20City%20and%20Migration%20barriers%2C%20practices%20and%20imaginaries.pdf>

Abstract

Drawing on the work of Henri Lefebvre, the seminar examines the right to the city for migrant populations. Through examples of research and projects carried out in various urban contexts, it highlights both material and symbolic barriers that limit access to urban spaces and full citizenship. Particular attention is given to the use of creative and participatory methods to narrate, analyse and imagine fairer and more inclusive cities. This seminar is part of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Right to the city; Migrant populations; Barriers; Urban spaces; Creative methods

International seminar

Movilidades humanas. Buenas prácticas para proteger en la desprotección

(Human mobilities. Good practices to protect in contexts vulnerability)

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Bienvenida institucional (*Institutional welcome*)

M^a Belén Morata García de la Puerta (University of Granada), Lucía López (Red Acoge) and Norma Montesino (University of Lund)

VIOLENCIA DE GÉNERO: PRECARIEDAD LEGAL Y MICROESPACIOS DE PROTECCIÓN (*GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE: LEGAL PRECARIETY AND MICRO-SPACES OF PROTECTION*)

Claudia Di Matteo (University of Lund)

MESA REDONDA: RESULTADOS DE ESTUDIOS DE CASO GLOBAL-ANSWER (*ROUNDTABLE: CASE STUDY RESULTS FROM THE GLOBAL-ANSWER PROJECT*)

Programa de atención humanitaria y respuestas alternativas fuera del programa desde las organizaciones sociales (*Global-ANSWER humanitarian assistance programme and alternative responses beyond the programme from civil society organisations*)

Lucía López, coordinadora de igualdad de trato y participación comunitaria y Carolina Vicente, responsable de protección internacional (*Lucía López coordinator for equal treatment and community participation and Carolina Vicente, head of international protection*) (Red Acoge)

El papel de los/as profesionales de origen extranjero de los servicios de acogida y de las asociaciones de personas migrantes" (*The role of migrant-origin professionals in reception services and migrant associations*)

Giuseppina Tumminelli and Roberta di Rosa (University of Palermo)

MESA REDONDA: EXPERIENCIAS DE INCLUSIÓN DESDE LA SOCIEDAD CIVIL (*ROUNDTABLE: INCLUSION EXPERIENCES FROM CIVIL SOCIETY*)

Movilidad desprotegida, voces migrantes (*Unprotected mobility, migrant voices*)

Papa Idy (Granafrik Association)

Roxana Gutiérrez Portugal (Nosotras Association)

Diade Sokhona (D. Bosco Foundation)

Marina Georgieva (D. Bosco Foundation)

Salif Coulybaly (D. Bosco Foundation)

Moderated by: Paula Rodríguez Aznar (University of Granada)

Comentarios, resumen, conclusiones (Comments, summary, conclusions)

Priscilla Solano (University of Lund) María Auxiliadora Trujillo (ÖDOS Programme) - Community Participation

Clausura (Closing)

Lucía López & Norma Montesino

University of Granada, July 8, 2025

Link to the seminar:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1JuXE42sIr80a75OUgMyGGcmaF4Fscodg/view?usp=sharing>

Abstract

This symposium is part of the “*Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region*” project (H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209). Unlike other symposia in the project, this event represented a mandatory activity within Global-ANSWER and showcased the strong collaboration between multiple partners, including Lund University, the University of Granada, the University of Palermo and Red Acoge. Held on July 8, 2025, at the Faculty of Social Work of the University of Granada, the symposium was dedicated to identifying and disseminating good practices aimed at ensuring protection in contexts of vulnerability and abandonment that characterize human mobility. The day opened with institutional greetings, followed by a focus on a crucial theme: gender-based violence in relation to legal precarity, examining the existing micro-spaces of protection. The core of the meeting was a round table discussing the results of the Global-ANSWER case studies, where humanitarian reception programs and alternative responses implemented by social organizations were presented. The significant participation of Red Acoge was highlighted, contributing to the discussion on protection and inclusion perspectives within the Spanish reception system. Particular emphasis was placed on the essential role of foreign-born professionals working in reception services and migrant associations. Beyond the institutional round table, the event gave prominence to the analysis of direct inclusion experiences through “migrant voices.” Representatives from key associations such as Granafrik, “Nosotras” and the D. Bosco Foundation shared first-hand reflections on mobility experienced under conditions of non-protection, fostering an equitable dialogue between experiential and academic knowledge. The discussions developed during the symposium reaffirm the importance of human rights-based approaches that acknowledge migrants as epistemic and operational partners in the co-production of knowledge and social innovation. The symposium concluded with reflections, a summary of the main outcomes and an emphasis on the importance of community participation, marking the official closure of the event.

Keywords: Human mobility; Good practices; Gender-based violence; Inclusion; Migrant voices

International seminar

Experiencias de investigación en trabajo social sobre personas migrantes (III Jornadas internacionales)

(Research experiences in social work on migrants (3rd International Conference))

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Chair:

Ana Huesca (Pontifical University Comillas)

Participants:

Antonella Nobile (Municipality of Palermo): “Dell'accoglienza dei MSNA nei progetti SAI e l'avvio verso l'avvio verso l'Autonomia” (*Reception of unaccompanied foreign minors (UAMs) in SAI projects and pathways towards autonomy*)

Anna Rita di Cola (Municipality of Palermo, Casa dei Diritti): “Accoglienza nei Progetti SAI Ordinari e identificazione precoce dei sopravvissuti alla violenza intenzionale” (*Reception in Ordinary SAI Projects and early identification of survivors of intentional violence*)

Elvira Korp (Linnaeus University) “Conditional inclusion: Work permits as a tool for selective border policy”

Pontifical University Comillas, October 22, 2025

Link to the seminar:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/182gTRHSjTgPh0iphMiUp_GS4eYkaxlx0/view?usp=sharing

Abstract

These sessions, which are the third to be held within the framework of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), form part of the dissemination activities of the Pontifical University Comillas and highlight the research experiences of the various participants in order to achieve improvements in research methodologies and subsequent intervention with migrant populations. Two social workers from the Municipality of Palermo, who work directly with this type of population, presented their work, and there was an exchange of practices among those attending. Likewise, an interesting debate took place with the representative from Linnaeus University, aiming to compare the different systems: Spanish, Italian, and Swedish.

Keywords: Research methodologies; Migration intervention; Comparative social systems; Professional practice exchange; Euro-Mediterranean cooperation

International seminar

Final del proyecto Global-ANSWER

“Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro- Mediterranean region”

(FINAL EVENT OF THE GLOBAL-ANSWER PROJECT)

Initiative organized by the Global-ANSWER network

Preside (Chair):

Ana Huesca (Pontifical University Comillas)

Bienvenida institucional (Institutional welcome)

Virginia Cagigal, Decana de la Facultad de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales (Dean of the Faculty of Human and Social Sciences) (Pontifical University Comillas)

Ponencia (Lecture):

Belén Morata (University of Granada) “Más allá de la movilidad: Las contribuciones del proyecto Global-ANSWER a la innovación y a la intervención en los Servicios Sociales” (*Beyond mobility: The contributions of the Global-ANSWER project to innovation and intervention in Social Services*)

Mesa redonda (Roundtable):

Moderated by Almudena Juárez (Pontifical University Comillas)

Lucía López (Red Acoge) “Programa de atención humanitaria y respuestas alternativas fuera del programa desde las organizaciones sociales” (*Humanitarian assistance program and alternative responses outside the program from social organizations*)

Laura Lorello (Linnaeus University) “Identità di genere e protezione internazionale” (*Gender identity and international protection*)

Elvira Korp (Linnaeus University) “Navigating Migration Policy in Sweden: Precarity, Uncertainty, and Rapid Changes”

Giorgia Bulli (University of Florence) “Implicaciones en la política de la movilidad humana en España e Italia” (*Implications of human mobility policy in Spain and Italy*)

Ana Huesca (Pontifical University Comillas) “Desafíos sobre la movilidad humana en la Europa actual” (*Challenges of human mobility in contemporary Europe*)

Debate, reflexión final en grupos y clausura (*Debate, final reflexion in groups and closing*)

Pontifical University Comillas, November 13, 2025

Link to the seminar:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/10VCKY5PLXv6kPtSWHVdLeUwBKEFbSd1d/view?usp=sharing>

Abstract

This seminar, organized by the University Comillas, is presented to attendees as an event marking the conclusion of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209). After a series of sessions and seminars held over the past years, this event features the institutional presence of the Dean of the Faculty of Human and Social Sciences, as well as Belén Morata, from the University of Granada and the Principal Investigator of the project, who, in her address, presents the results related to good practices and innovation in social work with immigrants and refugees. The other participants focus on various topics of interest, such as intervention by social organisations, the gender perspective in international protection, uncertainties in Swedish migration policies, the political implications of these issues, and the challenges Europe will face in the coming years. It is to be hoped that the messages disseminated through the reflections developed over the years within the Global-Answer Project have influenced the training of students at the University Comillas.

Keywords: Social work innovation; Migration policies; Good practices; International protection; Euro-Mediterranean cooperation

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Partner country conference

The enclosures and sadness of migrant categories

Norma Montesino (University of Lund)

In Problematizing migrations: mobility and vulnerablization in an age of abandonment and inequalities

Organized by the University of Palermo

Palermo, July 17-19, 2023

Link to the conference:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/sc.psicol.pedag.edellaformazione/.content/documenti/Eventi/Program-Conference-Problematizing-Migration.pdf>

Abstract

I think about the very language we use that does not allow us to capture what makes sense. I want to dwell first on the obstacles represented in the institutionalised language internalised in our bodies, an obstacle or much more than an obstacle, a prison that condemns and chains us to a perception of the world that keeps us where we are. I start thinking about the categories of difference. Specifically, the categories whose contents enclose the understanding of human mobilities in the semantics of sadness. These are categories with which I have lived, experiencing the sadness of confinement and to which I return today, identifying this time the origin of the discomfort that accompanied me in being named by others or in having to name others, categories to which I return today to understand the why and what of their contents. Rossi Braidotti's theory can be understood as affirmative action, where humans and non-humans interrelate, enhancing capacities, recognizing themselves as part of the world. This is a great challenge that contains different potentials and a liberating one because it leads us to leave the prisons in which we are locked up. They are confinements that condemn us to despair and collective depression that transforms us into slaves of the same system that destroys us. In the pain of repression, of the daily struggle against impotence, humiliation, the most elementary brutality, there are creativity that strength lies, relating to each other human and non-human create new forms of relationships, they defend joy, they discover and demonstrate together the possibility of resistance, despite the time, despite what came after and what they live today that other worlds are possible. This presentation is part of the Horizon project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-Answer - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Sad categories; Human mobilities; Resistance

Partner country conference

The institutional logics and the classification processes of gender-based violence (GBV): categorizations of provisions accessed by migrant women having a precarious legal status within secondary welfare provisions in Italy and Sweden

Claudia Di Matteo (University of Lund)

In Problematizing migrations: mobility and vulnerablization in an age of abandonment and inequalities

Organized by the University of Palermo

Palermo, July 17-19, 2023

Link to the conference:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/sc.psicol.pedag.edellaformazione/.content/documenti/Eventi/Program-Conference-Problematizing-Migration.pdf>

Abstract

The text examines how gendered and racialized power relations within border regimes impact migrant women, particularly in terms of their precarious legal status and exposure to violence. These dynamics influence how migrant women are categorized by the state and their access to welfare resources in advanced welfare societies. Since traditional welfare systems often fail to address the risks faced by migrant women with unstable legal status, NGOs, faith-based organizations, and voluntary groups provide crucial support in the areas of gender and migration. The study highlights how professionals interpret migrant women's needs, especially in relation to gender-based violence (GBV), and how these interpretations shape the social responses and services available to them. Using semi-structured interviews and qualitative vignettes, the study explores how secondary welfare actors in Italy and Sweden influence migrant women's access to social rights and services, with consequences for de-bordering and re-bordering practices. This work is part of the Horizon project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-Answer - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Gendered violence; Legal status; Welfare access; Border regimes

International conference

From “lost” to “productive” time in the reception system: challenges for the forced migrant’s right to study and lifelong learning

Alberto Tonini (University of Florence)

In 2024 Education & Health Research Hub Conference “College Students of Immigrant Origin: Research, Practice & Community Engagement”

Organized by the Center for Social Science Research and the Institute for Immigration Research of George Mason University

Online, February 1-2, 2024

Link to the abstract:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/7-2024%20Education%20%26%20Health%20Research%20Hub%20Conference.pdf>

Link to the conference:

<https://cssr.gmu.edu/events/15026>

Abstract

The paper examines the structural, cultural and social barriers that perpetuate discrimination and inequity in access to university education for asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection across Europe. It further explores the pivotal role universities can play in fostering human rights protection within a framework of equity and social justice. The paper is structured in two parts. The first section contextualizes the right to education, emphasizing the significance of lifelong learning while analysing the inherent ambiguities and contradictions within European asylum policies and reception systems. These systems often fluctuate between charitable interventions and control mechanisms, effectively transforming forced migrants from “historical and political subjects” into “objects of care”. This process results in the reification of asylum seekers and refugees as “bare life” dependent on assistance, which in turn becomes the foundational principle justifying their discrimination. The second section delves into the importance of the right to education as a means of healing biographical fractures. It highlights how education enables the reconstruction of interrupted schooling and addresses aspirations for a dignified life. Finally, the paper illustrates exemplary practices implemented by European universities aimed at reducing the discrepancy between the educational aspirations of forced migrants and the actual educational opportunities available in countries of settlement. These academic actions have become part of the good practices highlighted within the framework of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER - H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Discrimination; Right to education; Asylum seekers; Social justice; European universities

Partner country conference

Empadronamiento e Arraigo in Spagna: il contributo del Servicio de Atención al Inmigrante (SAI) del Comune di Granada

(Empadronamiento and Arraigo in Spain: the contribution of the Servicio de Atención al Inmigrante (SAI) of the Municipality of Granada)

Ivana Acocella (University of Florence)

In La presa in carico congiunta dei cittadini stranieri. Le consulenze specializzate dello Sportello Immigrazione del Comune di Firenze e l'integrazione con i servizi sociali.

Organized by the Immigration Desk and the Social Services Office of the Municipality of Florence

Florence, February 14, 2024

Link to the abstract:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/11-La%20presa%20in%20carico%20congiunta%20dei%20cittadini%20stranieri.pdf>

Link to the conference:

<https://www2.immigrazione.regione.toscana.it/sites/default/files/Programma%20seminario%2014%20febbraio%202024.jpg>

Abstract

The presentation addresses the procedures of *Empadronamiento* and *Arraigo* in Spain, as well as the role played by the *Servicio de Atención al Inmigrante* (SAI) of the Municipality of Granada in these processes. In particular, regarding *Empadronamiento*, the focus will be on the registration of irregular migrants in the municipal registry. Concerning *Arraigo*, attention will be directed towards the ordinary regularization procedure aimed at migrant integration, which is established through family, social, or economic ties. The paper thus aims to share knowledge about procedures and institutional expertise developed in other European countries in the fields of social protection and human mobility. It is part of the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), which seeks to foster international and interdisciplinary cooperation by promoting the exchange of good practices through its network of scholars and professionals.

Keywords: Empadronamiento; Arraigo; Irregular migrants; Social protection; Human mobility

Partner country conference

Legalità precaria del migrante in Italia. Evoluzione nel sistema normativo

(*Precarious legality of migrants in Italy: Evolution within the legal system*)

Ivana Acocella (University of Florence)

In Tavola Rotonda: Migranti e sfruttamento economico in Italia

Organized by the University of Florence

Florence, March 20, 2024

Link to the abstract:

https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/12-Conferenza%20Migranti%20e%20sfruttamento%20economico%20in%20Italia_.pdf

Link to the conference:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/art-514-tavola-rotonda-migranti-e-sfruttamento-economico-in-italia.html>

Abstract

The intervention at the round table aims to explore the ambivalences and contradictions that characterize national legislation on the entry and residence of foreign workers in Italy. Specifically, the analysis focuses on the so-called “Turco-Napolitano” law (Law 40/1998 and its Consolidation Act – Legislative Decree 286/1998), which regulates the migration of non-EU citizens to the country. Particular attention is given to the fundamental pillars of the original legal framework, designed to ensure a policy of controlled and legal entry and residence, while promoting an immigration model capable of fostering long-term stabilisation. The second part of the contribution examines how subsequent amendments to Legislative Decree 286/1998 – particularly the Bossi-Fini Law (Law 189/2002) and the security decrees introduced since 2008 – impose stricter regulations and introduce destabilising elements for the presence of foreign workers in Italy. The focus is on how these measures affect the three basic pillars of the original 1998 law – work, family unity, and residence – by weakening the legal status of migrant workers, thereby increasing their risk of precariousness and instability and contributing to occupational segregation and exploitation. The discussion on non-EU workers draws on the entry “Migrant Worker” in the Glossary on Good Practices in the Field of Social Work and Human Mobility (edited by Gijón Sánchez and Morata García de la Puerta; Global-ANSWER Network “Social Work and Human Mobility”, 2023), developed within the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Precarious Legality; Migrants; Italy; Regulatory System

Partner country conference

Hacia la construcción colaborativa de una definición de buenas prácticas en el ámbito del trabajo social y la movilidad humana

(Towards the collaborative construction of a definition of good practices in the field of social work and human mobility)

María Teresa Gijón Sánchez (University of Granada)
M. Belén Morata García de la Puerta (University of Granada)
Gaetano Gucciardo (University of Palermo)

*In V Congreso Internacional de Trabajo Social (CIFETS 2024)
"Con-ciencia del trabajo social, en tiempos de transiciones globales"*

Málaga, April 17-19, 2024

Link to the program:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Tf4TLYduTjiAuF8uAnC_Pkt2PzWbSryn/view?usp=sharing

Abstract

Introduction. A good practice can be defined in multiple ways. However, it commonly refers to any method, process, or action that has proven to be well-planned, beneficial, and transferable across a variety of situations and contexts within a given disciplinary and/or professional field. This work presents the methodological process of collaboratively constructing a definition of good practices applied to the field of social work and human mobility, carried out by the Global-ANSWER Network. *Methods.* The Global-ANSWER Network was established within the framework of the project “Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region” funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 872209. The Network consists of researchers from universities and professionals from fifteen public and third sector organizations in Spain, Italy, and Sweden. Its aim is to identify, analyse, and disseminate good practices in the field of social work research and intervention with migrant, refugee, or asylum-seeking populations. To this end, its members have engaged in an inductive, collaborative, and participatory methodological process aimed at reaching consensus, through which they have constructed a definition of good practices based on the exchange of skills, experiences, and knowledge acquired in different migratory contexts, serving as a foundation for designing and implementing these practices in others. *Results.* Preliminary results indicate that, for the Global-ANSWER Network, a good practice is one that includes four interrelated identifying components: coherence, awareness, reflexivity and sustainability. Furthermore, it must promote the inclusion of all actors without any form of discrimination, from an intersectional perspective and encourage their effective participation in proposing solutions aimed at fostering the social inclusion of individuals and groups in vulnerable situations as a result of global mobility. It is an open-ended definition, currently being reassessed through various case studies with the goal of exchanging, transferring, and disseminating knowledge. *Discussion and Conclusions.* Spain, Italy and Sweden represent significant contexts from which to observe the social and political implications of human mobility in understanding contemporary migration phenomena. All three countries have played a strategic and central role in facing this challenge, albeit with significant differences among them, due to their diverse geopolitical situations and specific economic, social, and territorial characteristics. The challenge of collaboratively constructing a definition of good practices to promote the social inclusion of migrant, refugee, or asylum-seeking populations is essential for building more cohesive and just societies in Europe, where all individuals have the opportunity to participate and contribute fully without discrimination, in line with the international principles and values of Social Work as an academic discipline and profession.

Keywords: Social work; Human mobility; Good practices; Social inclusion; Knowledge transfer.

Partner country conference

Una reflexión teórica del concepto de innovación social y su operacionalización en el campo del trabajo social y la movilidad humana

(A theoretical reflection on the concept of social innovation and its operationalization in the field of social work and human mobility)

M. Belén Morata García de la Puerta (University of Granada)

María Teresa Gijón Sánchez (University of Granada)

*In V Congreso Internacional de Trabajo Social (CIFETS 2024)
"Con-ciencia del trabajo social, en tiempos de transiciones globales"*

Malaga, April 17-19, 2024

Link to the program:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Tf4TLYduTjiAuF8uAnC_Pkt2PzWbSryn/view?usp=sharing

Abstract

In recent decades, literature on social innovation has expanded widely, both as a concept and as a working process. In the field of human mobility and social work, evidence shows that there is no consensus on its conceptualization and operationalization. However, since the 2000s, a common denominator has been its use by diverse actors (governments, social entities of all kinds, commercial enterprises, universities, and higher education organizations) to reduce social problems and improve people's quality of life, as well as to enhance the social economy through the co-production of outcomes. This work is the result of the analysis conducted by the Global-ANSWER Network, within the framework of the European project "Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region" funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program through the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 872209 (2022–2025). Through a review of international literature, an attempt has been made to reach a joint definition of social innovation that identifies the main factors contributing to its conceptualization. The heterogeneity of findings prevents the current assessment of the contributions that literature identifies as social innovation interventions with migrants and, consequently, hinders the transfer of this knowledge into professional practice, even in seemingly similar contexts. In the field of social work and human mobility, a shared definition would serve to improve knowledge transfer, contributing effectively to promoting positive and transformative change in the social inclusion of migrants in host societies.

Keywords: Social innovation; Social work; Human mobility; Knowledge transfer; Global-ANSWER

International conference

Panel “Human mobility in social services. Insights from the Global- ANSWER project”

Comparative analysis of regional reception systems for migrants in Tuscany and Andalusia: criticism and values

Ivana Acocella (University of Florence)

The governance of migration at the local level: refugee services in Tuscany

Stella Milani (University of Florence)

A comparative analysis of immigration, reception systems and housing policies: the case of Andalusia and Tuscany

Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence)

The institutional discourse on migration: rights, policies and social services in Tuscany

Silvia Pezzoli (University of Florence)

Politicizing migration in a local context. The Andalusian case

Giorgia Bulli (University of Florence)

Social services for labour integration in the local context

Annalisa Tonarelli (University of Florence)

In 6TH International Scientific Conference: Achievements and Challenges of Social Work Profession

Organized by the University of Tirana, May 23, 2024

Link to the abstract:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/8%20TH%20International%20Scientific%20Conference.pdf>

Link to the conference:

<https://unitir.edu.al/en/konference-nderkombetare-per-sfidat-e-punonjesit-social/>

Abstract

The panel presents the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), with the aim of highlighting the contribution of the University of Florence. Specifically, the University of Florence’s case study aims to describe and analyse the characteristics of regional reception systems (for migrants in general and asylum seekers/refugees in particular) in Tuscany and Andalusia, within the political, cultural and social context of each region. The comparison focuses on key variables such as socio-demographic characteristics of immigration, immigrant integration policies, the actors involved and the role of the third sector in the management of migrant reception and integration. The study includes an analysis of decision-making: how local administrators – depending on their political affiliation, but also on their assessment of external events – interpret the phenomenon of immigration and make key decisions regarding the organization of the reception system in their territories. These decisions include aspects such as the availability of reception services, commitment to the establishment of reception facilities and the implementation of socio-economic and cultural inclusion programs. Through a qualitative investigation, comparative case studies focus on the reception systems for persons in need of international protection, aiming to contextualize the phenomenon in both regions and to identify good practices as well as critical issues in reception.

Keywords: Migration; Reception; Integration; Local governance; Good practices

Partner country conference

Pratiche del lavoro sociale nel sistema di accoglienza ed integrazione

(Social work practices in the reception and integration system)

Santa Giuseppina Tuminelli (University of Palermo)

In IV Conferenza Italiana sulla Ricerca di Servizio Sociale (CIRSS)

Lecce, June 6-8, 2024

Link to the program: <https://www.sociss.it/programma/>

Abstract

The paper aims to present the results of a research study carried out in Palermo on the Reception and Integration System (SAI). The study is part of the project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), involving Italy, Spain and Sweden. The objective was to analyse how the SAI functions at the local level, identifying the reception model, processes, and practices implemented by the Social Services of the Municipality of Palermo. The SAI has been considered a good practice at the national level, particularly due to its role as "part of the process of revitalization and development of the country's most fragile and marginal areas" (Accorinti, Giovannetti 2023: 8). The research was structured into two phases. In the first phase, several theoretical approaches were adopted, including Bolzman's (2009) classification of five general models of social work with migrant populations, the distinction between the cultural competence/sensitivity approach and the anti-discrimination approach (Barberis, Boccagni, 2017), and the intersectional approach (Crenshaw, 1989). A reflexive perspective was also used as a key tool for understanding and evaluating different discourses, enabling innovative responses and applying the principle of "mobilizing potential" (Cesareo, Pavesi 2019), which supports complex responses to diverse needs. In the second phase, the SAI was analysed as an example of good practice, based on a definition co-constructed by researchers and professionals within the Global-ANSWER network. This definition identified four essential criteria to ensure that practices are effective and aligned with ethical and professional standards: coherence in design, awareness during implementation, reflexivity in the monitoring process, and sustainability in relation to impact. The empirical research was guided by three foundational questions: ontological (concerning the nature of the object studied), epistemological (concerning the production of scientific knowledge) and methodological (regarding social research methods as a systematic body of techniques) (Corbetta, 1999, pp. 21–23). The techniques used included biographical interviews (Bichi, 2002), participant observation (Cardano, 2011), and focus groups. The research confirmed the value of cross-pollination between the knowledge developed through social work practice and that produced in academic contexts, and it highlighted the presence of transformative actors—individuals capable of initiating change and generating innovative and alternative solutions.

Keywords: Social work; Human mobility; Good practices; Reception; Integration System (SAI); Reflexivity

Partner country conference

Usera between urban transformations, borders and multiculturalism

Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence)

In Society for the Study of Symbolic Interaction – European Society for the Study of Symbolic Interaction (SSSI) 2024 Annual meeting “Identities, boundaries and social divisions. Reconciling competing frames”

Pisa, June 5-7, 2024

Link to the abstract:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/9-Society%20for%20the%20Study%20of%20Symbolic%20Interaction.pdf>

Link to the conference:

<https://grounded-theory.sp.unipi.it>

Abstract

The paper presents research on the Usera district in Madrid, one of the city's most multicultural areas, focusing on the integration of various migration groups, both external and internal, from different historical periods. Usera, a relatively new district (established in 1987), is made up of seven neighbourhoods with distinct histories, populated by diverse nationalities, including Roma, Moroccans, Latin Americans, Chinese and Spaniards. The study adopts a multidisciplinary approach, combining sociology and history and is structured around three main concepts: urban transformation, borders, and multiculturalism. It examines the neighbourhood's evolution, including gentrification processes triggered by the construction of the metro and the M-30 highway, as well as the recent real estate bubble. The concept of borders is explored in both spatial and mnemonic terms: the northern part of the district is linked to older internal migrations (1950s–1960s), while the southern part is associated with more recent internal and external migrations (1960s–1990s). The "memory border" connects past migrations with current ones in relation to identity and countries of origin. The study also analyses multiculturalism and integration, investigating whether the presence of different social groups fosters mutual exchange or merely coexistence. This study is presented within the framework of the project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Multiculturalism; Urban transformation; Migration; Borders; Memory

Partner country conference

Riflessioni a partire dal testo: from the 'White Paper' of the Tuscany Region to replicable best practices

(Reflections based on the text: from the 'White Paper' of the Tuscany Region to replicable best practices)

Ivana Acocella (University of Florence)

Giorgia Bulli (University of Florence)

In Immigrazione e inclusione in Toscana: bilancio, progetti, prospettive

Organized in collaboration with the Region of Tuscany

Florence, May 29, 2025

Link to the program:

https://ancitoscana.it/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Immigrazione-e-inclusione-in-Toscana_programma-1.pdf

Abstract

The presentation begins with a brief overview of the project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), within which the publication *From the 'White Paper' of the Tuscany Region to Replicable Best Practices in the Reception of Persons in Need of International Protection* is produced. This is followed by an outline of the key principles underlying the governance model promoted by the Tuscany Region in the field of migration policies, as identified through the analysis of Regional Law No. 29 of 2009 and the guidelines of the *White Paper* drafted by the Tuscany Region and ANCI Toscana in 2017. Based on these principles and strategic orientations, several projects and services implemented across the regional territory—targeting immigrants in vulnerable conditions and recognized as best practices within the Global-ANSWER project—are presented. The final part features a selection of additional best practices identified in the project's partner countries, thanks to the comparative approach adopted. These practices offer useful insights for developing new interventions and services to be promoted within integration and social protection policies for migrants in Tuscany and across Italy.

Keywords: Migration; Best practices; Local governance; Integration

Partner country conference

Tra crisi ed emergenza. L'evoluzione dei discorsi politici, giuridici e giornalistici sulle migrazioni in Toscana tra concordanze e divergenze

(Between crisis and emergency. The evolution of political, legal, and journalistic discourses on migration in Tuscany between convergences and divergences)

Silvia Pezzoli (University of Florence)

In VII Convegno della Società Scientifica Italiana di Sociologia, Cultura, Comunicazione (SISCC 2025) "Non c'è più tempo! Crisi ed emergenze nella società contemporanea"

Cagliari, June 19-20, 2025

Link to the abstract:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/18-%20SISCC.pdf>

Link to the program:

<https://www.conftool.net/siscc2025/index.php?page=browseSessions>

Abstract

The Horizon 2020 project Global ANSWER – Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work, led by the University of Granada, aims to identify and share good practices in human mobility (migrants, refugees, asylum seekers) across Spain, Italy, and Sweden. It promotes research and training involving universities, municipalities, and third-sector organizations. One of the project's key areas of investigation is the comparison between the reception systems in Tuscany and Andalusia. This paper contributes to that focus by analysing regional legislation and political debates in Tuscany, specifically Regional Law 45/2019 and Law 29/2009. The study explores how regional administrations frame the migration phenomenon and how political affiliations shape the nature of policy debates. A second component of the research involves a comparison between political-administrative discourse and journalistic narratives produced during the approval process of the most recent law, based on analysis of the Tuscany Region's press review. The objective is to understand how migration is discursively constructed through various, yet interconnected, frames often associated with urgency and emergency, and how these frames affect public policy. The research investigates whether emergency framing in political discourse on migration varies over time, what types of laws and policies emerge from urgency-driven debates, and how media coverage influences the construction of migration discourse. The methodology consists of two phases. The first is a terminological content analysis of three types of texts – political (council debates), legal (the two laws), and journalistic (press review) – where key terms related to the concept of reception are identified and classified as favourable, unfavourable, or neutral. The second phase is a comparative analysis of terminology and language across legislative sessions and sources to trace the evolution of political, legal, and journalistic discourse. This comparison sheds light on how political and media narratives interact, shaping public perception of migration and influencing the success or failure of related policies. This study was conducted within the framework of “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-

Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER), funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 872209. The Agency and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Keywords: Migration; Discourse (political, legal, journalistic); Reception

International conference

The creation of an integrated governance model for reception and integration measures for asylum seekers and refugees: the role of social workers in SAI projects in the Tuscany region

Ivana Acocella (University of Florence)

Costanza Gasparo (University of Florence)

Stella Milani (University of Florence)

In 2025 European Conference on Social Work Education "Social Connectedness - Contemporary Challenges and Opportunities" (ECSWE 2025)

Salzburg, June 23-26, 2025

Link to the abstract:

[https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/17-%20ECSWE%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/17-%20ECSWE%20(1).pdf)

Link to the program:

https://ecswe2025-salzburg.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/ECSWE_Program_2606.pdf

Abstract

This paper explores the development of an integrated governance model for the reception and integration of asylum seekers and refugees in Tuscany, Italy. At the heart of this model are two main features: (a) multi-professional teams and (b) a multidisciplinary approach engaging local associations, institutions, and resources (Gori 2019). This approach aligns with the 2017 *White Paper on Reception Policies for Asylum Seekers and International or Humanitarian Protection Holders*, which set the foundation for coordinated reception policies across Tuscany. The model's implementation has involved pairing individual municipality-led SAI (System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees) centres with collaborative governance structures through Unions of Municipalities and Health Societies. This paper examines three governance models within the SAI framework: those managed by individual municipalities, those led by Municipal Unions, and those overseen by Health Societies. Each governance approach aims to enhance resource sharing and service integration to foster a more cohesive reception system. Focusing on the role of social workers and local social services in SAI teams, the study underscores their role in bridging SAI interventions and local welfare services. Drawing on qualitative research and in-depth interviews with key figures from SAI across Tuscany, this study highlights variations in resources, operational flexibility, and strategic roles across governance models, identifying best practices and challenges. This research is part of the Horizon project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-ANSWER- H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Governance model; Asylum seekers; Multidisciplinary approach; SAI (System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees); Social workers

International conference

Approches internationales des recherches universitaires sur le travail social. La place spécifique des enseignants-chercheurs comme médiateur du décloisonnement des savoirs

as part of the

"Table ronde: animée par Gisèle Dambuyant"

(International approaches to university research on social work: the specific role of academic researchers as mediators in bridging knowledge gaps as part of the "Round Table: chaired by Gisèle Dambuyant")

Annalisa Tonarelli (University of Florence)

In 34^e REFUTS international colloquium "Les formes d'engagement entre recherche, formation et intervention sociale: un enjeu de service à la société"

Belgium, June 25-27, 2025

Link to the abstract:

<https://www.dsps.unifi.it/upload/sub/REFUTS.pdf>

Link to the conference:

<https://iitse.ulb.be/en/agenda/34-refuts-international-colloquium>

Abstract

What role do Italian *enseignants-chercheurs* (teacher-researchers) play in the field of social intervention? What stance do they take toward the beneficiaries of the social inclusion projects they are involved in? Do they speak about them, on their behalf, or do they contribute to giving them a voice? Is this issue discussed among academic and non-academic actors working within the migrant reception system in Italy? The roundtable intervention will begin with these questions, aiming to find some answers through a reflection on the research and mobility experiences carried out within the project “Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region” (Global-ANSWER – H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209), which made it possible to explore and compare migrant reception models in Tuscany and Andalusia.

Keywords: Social intervention; Social inclusion projects; Migrant reception system; Teacher-researchers

Partner country conference

Il benessere organizzativo nel sistema di accoglienza: prospettive degli assistenti sociali dal progetto H2020 Global-ANSWER

(Organizational wellbeing in the reception system: social workers' perspectives from the H2020 Global-ANSWER project)

Carla Zappulla (Università di Palermo)

Flavia Cirimele (Università di Palermo)

Roberta T. Di Rosa (Università di Palermo)

In La medicina transculturale: sfide e prospettive interdisciplinari per l'accoglienza e la cura

Organized by University of Palermo

Agrigento, October 10-11, 2025

Link to the conference:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/promise/La-medicina-transculturale-sfide-e-prospettive-interdisciplinari-tra-laccoglienza-e-la-cura---riconoscimento-CFU/>

Link to the program:

https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/promise/.content/documenti/Convegno-medicina-Transculturale-10_11-ottobe-2025-Last.pdf

Abstract

Introduction. In the migrant reception system, social workers play a crucial role in supporting and safeguarding the rights and well-being of migrants in a foreign country. However, their work is highly demanding in terms of time, effort, and emotional and social impact: social workers interact daily not only with the migrants' stories of vulnerability but also contribute to creating collective well-being with the local population. The well-being of migrants is therefore at the center of the social worker's mission, often at the expense of their own well-being. As a result, they frequently experience burnout syndrome (a condition characterized by exhaustion, cynicism, and inefficacy caused by chronic emotional and interpersonal stressors). Based on these considerations, this exploratory study focuses on the well-being of social workers operating in the field of migration, examining how levels of burnout are associated with individuals' empathy and sensitivity toward different cultures and backgrounds.

Participants and instruments. The study involved 38 social workers aged between 30 and 60 years ($M = 39.63$), from Italy ($N = 8$), Spain ($N = 23$), and Sweden ($N = 7$).

To collect information on the three dimensions considered (burnout, intercultural sensitivity, and empathy), the following questionnaires were administered via an online platform: the Burnout Assessment Tool (BAT, 23-item; Consiglio et al., 2021; Schaufeli & De Witte, 2023); the Intercultural Sensitivity Scale (short form, 15 items; Wang & Zhou, 2016); and the Prosociality Scale (4-item; Caprara et al., 2005; Luengo Kanacri et al., 2021).

Analysis and results. Two types of analysis were conducted:

(a) analysis of variance (ANOVA) to identify differences among social workers across countries;

(b) identification of subgroups with high and low burnout (above and below the 50th percentile) for a qualitative analysis of profiles in the three countries.

The ANOVAs revealed significant differences among social workers in Italy, Spain, and Sweden regarding mental distance at work, attentiveness in interactions when communicating with people from different backgrounds, and empathy. Specifically, in Spain, compared to Italy and Sweden, higher levels of burnout (mental distance) emerged. In Sweden, compared to Spain and Italy, lower levels of empathy and attentiveness in interactions with migrants were observed, along with greater vulnerability to burnout among younger social workers.

Profile assessments of social workers across the three countries showed that high burnout is associated in Italy with higher empathy and emotional involvement in interactions, but lower trust and intercultural attentiveness; in Spain, with lower respect for cultural differences and reduced enjoyment of interactions; and in Sweden, with lower involvement, lower respect, lower self-confidence, but higher attentiveness during interactions.

Concluding considerations. These findings suggest several reflections:

(a) National and systemic differences (types of services, organizational support, specific training) highlight the importance of targeted

organizational policies and professional training to reduce burnout and promote resilience among social workers.

(b) The high levels of burnout identified point to the need for constant monitoring of professionals' well-being to safeguard the professional-client relationship and the ability to provide culturally competent services.

(c) The relevance of intercultural skills and confidence in interactions underscores the need for targeted interventions (e.g., role-playing, modelling) to strengthen self-efficacy and, in turn, professional effectiveness.

(d) Differences in empathy profiles across countries show that, although empathy is crucial for a person-centered approach, context-specific supervision, psychological support, and empowerment strategies are needed to ensure that empathy functions as a protective rather than a risk factor. This research is part of the Horizon project Global-ANSWER (H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209).

Keywords: Social Workers; Migrants; Burnout; Empathy; Intercultural Sensitivity

Partner country conference

Disabilità e migrazioni: diseguglianze nell'accesso alla cura

(Disability and migration: inequalities in access to care)

Giuseppina Tumminelli (Università di Palermo)

In La medicina transculturale: sfide e prospettive interdisciplinare per l'accoglienza e la cura

Organized by University of Palermo

Agrigento, October 10-11, 2025

Link to the conference:

<https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/promise/La-medicina-transculturale-sfide-e-prospettive-interdisciplinari-tra-laccoglienza-e-la-cura---riconoscimento-CFU/>

Link to the program:

https://www.unipa.it/dipartimenti/promise/.content/documenti/Convegno-medicina-Transculturale-10_11-ottobe-2025-Last.pdf

Abstract

Talking about “disability” in reference to migrants means addressing a complex and often hidden issue, particularly due to the lack of data and information and the inadequacy of existing monitoring and research systems. In this specific context, disability is further amplified by the connection between mental/physical health and social disadvantage, generating unique conditions defined as the “triple barrier” to healthcare inequality: unequal determinants of mental health (related to the balance between risk and protective factors), inequitable access to mental health support, and differences in care experiences and outcomes (PICUM, 2022; Pasini, Merotta, 2023). The aim of this contribution is to present the first results of an exploratory study on the situation of migrants with disabilities within the Reception and Integration System (SAI) in the Palermo area, and to propose reflections on the critical issues emerging in the system in response to the needs of incoming migrants, as well as on the inequalities and disparities in access to socio-health services. This contribution is part of the European project Global-ANSWER, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 872209.

Keywords: Disability; Migrants; Mental Health; Social Disadvantage; Healthcare Inequality

Partner country conference

Panel “Buenas prácticas y movilidad humana: un enfoque innovador para la inclusión y la protección social”

(Good practices and human mobility: an innovative approach to inclusion and social protection)

Coordinators: M. Belén Morata García de la Puerta, Giorgia Bulli and Teresa Gijón Sánchez

Paper 1: Los tutores voluntarios de menores migrantes no acompañados en Italia: un referente para inserción (*Volunteer guardians for unaccompanied migrant minors in Italy: a reference model for inclusion*)

Raquel Vida Fernández (University of Granada)

Paper 2: Training language mediators to promote the integration of migrants in the community: An analysis of training programmes at the Universities of Bologna and Palermo

Mette Rudvin (University of di Palermo)

Paper 3: La resiliencia como clave para una intervención social con hijos e hijas de inmigrantes (*Resilience as a key to social intervention with the sons and daughters of immigrants*)

Claudia María Anleu Hernández (University of Rovira i Virgili)

Paper 4: Reception and Integration of Asylum Seekers and Refugees. The Contribution of Social Workers to Governance Models in Tuscany's SAI Projects

Ivana Acocella, Costanza Gasparo, Stella Milani (University of Florence)

Paper 5: Valoración de los programas para personas migrantes o solicitantes de asilo en Granada (*Resilience as a key to social intervention with the sons and daughters of immigrants*)

Ainhoa Rodríguez García de Cortázar e Paula Rodríguez Aznar (University of Granada)

Paper 6: El empadronamiento de las personas migrantes sin domicilio fijo en la provincia de Girona: precarización, politización y barreras para la innovación en la inclusión y la protección social (*Empadronamiento of homeless migrants in the province of Girona: precarization, politicization, and barriers to innovation in inclusion and social protection*)

Eduard Carrera Fossas, Carme Trull Oliva y Wafa Boulahrouz Lahmidi

Paper 7: Medidas/Herramientas para el acompañamiento de procesos de reagrupación de menores de origen extranjero (*Measures/tools for supporting the family reunification processes of foreign minors*)

Rubén Lasheras Ruiz, Edurne Jabat Torres e Izaskun Andueza Imirizaldu (Public University of Navarre)

Paper 8: Regímenes de (in)movilidad humana y prácticas de acompañamiento migrante (*(Im)mobility regimes and migrant accompaniment practices*)

Ignacio Fradejas García (University of Oviedo)

Paper 9: La intervención social con personas de origen extranjero en la atención primaria: Una aproximación desde la perspectiva de las profesionales

Arkaitz Fullaondo, Noemi Bergantiños, Lía González, Asier Galera (University of the Basque Country)

Paper 10: Between Protection and Precarity: Professional Intervention in Migrant Reception and Social Inclusion in Palermo's SAI System

Felicia Modica (University of Palermo)

Paper 11: El acompañamiento y la atención a jóvenes migrantes no acompañados desde el ámbito comunitario. Una experiencia de colaboración entre Sareak Josten y profesorado de la Facultad de RRL y Trabajo Social de la UPV/EHU (*Support and care for unaccompanied migrant youth at the community level: a collaboration experience between Sareak Josten and faculty from the School of Labour Relations and Social Work at UPV/EHU*)

Marina Sagastizabal; Lia Gonzalez; Ixone Fernandez de Labastida (University of the Basque Country – UPV/EHU)

Paper 12: Refugiados en España y Alemania: buenas prácticas comparadas (*Refugees in Spain and Germany: a comparative study of good practices*)

Ana Huesca, Almudena Juárez y Laura Zanón (Pontifical University Comillas)

In X Congreso de la Red Española de Política Social (REPS) "La dimensión social de las políticas públicas"

La Rioja, October 22-24, 2025

Link to the panel: <https://reps2025.unirioja.es/es/pages/paneles>

Link to the program: <https://reps2025.unirioja.es/es/pages/programa1>

Abstract

The intersection between human mobility and social protection is an area that requires academic and professional attention, since the social inclusion of migrants in host societies is one of the main challenges faced by the globalized world. Social protection must be a fundamental mechanism for guaranteeing human rights, especially in contexts of vulnerability (adequate social policies and the provision of basic services), promoting equal opportunities and universal access. However, the well-being of this population is not always guaranteed. They are often in a situation of vulnerability due to restrictions and the limited impact of social protection policies. Their irregular administrative status and economic precariousness are some of the factors that turn those who have had to leave their countries of origin in search of better life opportunities into second-class citizens. The value of good practices and the possibility of sharing them is highlighted, to identify successful strategies that have been effective in different contexts. These are concrete examples of how professional action can inspire new initiatives and social policies that improve the well-being of migrant populations. Reference is also made to social innovation, understood as the development of new approaches and solutions to social problems, acting effectively and efficiently, and being sustainable. Finally, the phenomenon of human mobility is currently facing the rise of the far right and populist movements, which have raised the alarm and portray mobility as a threat to Western societies (blaming it for many of the problems faced by modernity). It is urgent to address these issues comprehensively, through an innovative approach. Research papers and professional experiences are welcome, focusing on some of the following subtopics: 1) Legal foundations and the rollback of the rights of migrants and asylum seekers in Europe. Future challenges. 2) Practices of (dis)protection and limits of professional intervention in the field of human mobility. 3) Good practices and innovative protection experiences for migrants and applicants for international protection. 4) Elimination of borders: culture and identity, migrants and applicants for international protection in Europe, in dynamic and complex contexts. 5) Political discourse and the politicization of the migration debate. Social imaginaries and public opinion on human mobility in the 21st century. This panel will present the main developments of the Global-ANSWER Network (MSCA-RISE-2019, ID: 872209), although it is also open to other research that enriches the intellectual and professional debate on human mobility and professional intervention.

Keywords: Migration; Reception; Integration; Local governance; Good practices

SUMMER SCHOOL

Summer school

Newsmedia representation of migrants in Italy. Trends and perspectives

External initiative within the Global-ANSWER network involving members of the project team

Francesca Rizzuto (University of Palermo)

In 2023 Escuela de Verano Granada MIGRATION STUDIES PH.D. SUMMER SCHOOL (MISSCHO) "Representation, narratives and discourse on migration"

Institute for Migration Research, University of Granada, July 3-6, 2023

Link to the summer school:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IWVXEoYY2yxlymUsjB3i5dt3zhrBgJa_/view?usp=sharing

Abstract

The Migration Studies Ph.D. Summer School (MISSCHO) 2023 offered an intensive program focusing on discourse on migration issues. The seminar proposed by Francesca Rizzuto aimed at presenting the peculiar case of Italian news media narratives on migrants, underlining the role of journalism in the perception of the Other-Migrant. This is one of the central issues of the democratic debate, because the mediated description of migratory phenomenon, influences public opinion and offers a daily pervasive construction of the Other, which has deep consequences. After the presentation of the context of the Italian "traditionally weak and politicized" media system, the focus was on the process of journalistic construction of reality and its effects on individual perceptions and behaviours. Some cases of media representation strategies were analysed: fragmentation, depersonalization, decontextualization and, above all, the presence of a *Western* point of view produce a biased mirror of migration in Italy. In general, it was pointed out that Italian new media tend to offer a spectacular journalistic construction of migrants, based on commonplaces, where differences among individuals are *erased*, confirming prejudices on some ethnic groups. The "Other" is usually presented as a *cause* of problems: the most visible risk is that media representation of migrants as a *problem* proposes a superficial simplification of reality, using stereotypes to build an image based on the contrast between *Us/Them*, with a positive characterization for *us* and a negative characterization for *them*, because "us" implies order, rationality, solidarity; "them", on the contrary, makes reference to disorder, irrationality, need. In conclusion, the general trend of Italian media is the construction of a pseudo-reality, daily affirmed through the selection of some themes and emotional stories as well as the disappearance of some facts and dimensions. This study took place within the framework of "Global social work and human mobility: comparative studies on local government and good social work practices in the Euro-Mediterranean region" (Global-ANSWER), funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 872209.

Keywords: Media representation; Migration discourse; Othering

Summer school

Human mobility: best practices in a context of precarity and expulsions

External initiative within the Global-ANSWER network involving members of the project team

Norma Montesino (University of Lund)

In 2024 Escuela de Verano Granada MIGRATION STUDIES PH.D. SUMMER SCHOOL (MISSCHO) "Migration in the digital era: challenging theory, methods and practice"

Institute for Migration Research, University of Granada, July 8-11, 2024

Link to the summer school:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1kdPOFWqhQDIYSiPwpQtIWggnGkVoMih/view?usp=sharing>

Abstract

We are experiencing the consequences of neoliberal policies, which are accelerating climate change and producing ecological disasters, as well as the violence of war that follows in their wake. These destructive phenomena undermine established institutional orders and their foundations, highlighting the limits of our understanding of reality. It is in this context that we initiated the GLOBAL RESPONSE project, which was scheduled to begin in 2020. However, the global paralysis caused by the subsequent outbreak of the SARS-CoV-2 virus simultaneously highlighted the relevance of the project's objectives: to rethink social work from the perspective of those affected by forced mobility. Through interrelated processes, we analyse various situations, issues and responses to these mobilities, reflecting how this context of global transformation challenges the foundations of social work and its practices. This reflection carried out within the framework of the Horizon project "Global Social Work and Human Mobility: Comparative Studies on Local Government and Good Social Work Practices in the Euro-Mediterranean Region" (Global-ANSWER- H2020-MSCA-RISE-GA-872209). Today, scholars from different disciplines are reflecting on the ways in which the potential for collective thinking and action has been undermined. In their studies, they identify how economisation, the privatisation of public spaces and the process of individualisation – in short, neoliberalism – has reduced the opportunities for social interaction and undermined the social dimensions of human life. In this context, social workers mean that doing social work presupposes a meeting space, time to build a relationship, and empathy with the suffering of those affected by ongoing changes. Social workers argue that the fundamental requirements for doing social work are a physical space, time to develop relationships and empathy for those affected by ongoing changes. However, today, social workers are raising concerns about the difficulties they face in their daily work. The spaces available are shrinking and there is minimal or practically no time to think and act. They also emphasise the importance of understanding what is happening, as we are all affected by processes beyond our control that are destroying the ability to carry out social work. Social workers are raising concerns about the difficulties in daily work, where the time to think and act is minimal or practically non-existent. They also emphasize the willingness to understand what is happening, as we are all involved and affected by processes we do not control, processes that are destroying the possibilities of being, thinking, and doing social work.

Keywords: Social Work; Human mobility; Neoliberalism; Daily work

GLOBAL ANSWER

**Social work
and human mobility**